

SELF-EFFICACY FRAMEWORK AMONG ARABIC TEACHERS**Gaudencio G. Abellanosa****Caren A. Nisnisan****Liza Mae M. Maon****Nelmar G. Crausos****Elaine Jubailyn Mocsanat****Carlito B. Loro**College of Development and Management, University of Southeastern Philippines-Mintal Campus,
Mintal, Davao City 8000, Philippines**ABSTRACT**

The value of education remains steadfast through the test of time and the effectiveness of the educators plays a significant role in this. This study investigates the self-efficacy framework among Arabic educators in Davao del Norte, Philippines. Grounded in Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, the research examines how teachers' ability to foster student achievement is shaped by their individual experiences, professional development, and cultural context. A total of 150 Arabic teachers were identified as respondents. Through the rotated component matrix of the Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), two (2) were discarded out of the thirty (30) questions and it revealed eight (8) dimensions, including decision-making and resilience, supportive learning environments, behavioral management, parental involvement, resourcefulness and collaboration, School Resources and Instruction, and community engagement.

Keywords:

Self-efficacy, decision-making and resilience, creation of supportive learning environments, behavioral management, parental involvement, resourcefulness and collaboration, School Resources and Instruction, and community engagement

INTRODUCTION

Teachers face daily challenges in selecting effective teaching methods for students, particularly in reading. These obstacles are primarily due to a theoretical attitude towards reading and the influence of literacy theories, beliefs, and personal opinions on the reading process and student acquisition (Alfayez, 2022). Arifa and Faruq (2021) found that the most popular research themes among students were textbooks, Arabic speaking skills, linguistics, and vocabulary. However, the Arabic language teaching community and educators have unintentionally overlooked the psychological aspects of teaching Arabic. It was discovered that when educators possessed the self-efficacy skills necessary for the development of literacy, their pupils improved in literacy-related abilities. In 2005, the Saudi Ministry of Education introduced a new curriculum incorporating Arabic language proficiency in elementary and intermediate grades. However, teachers were unprepared and held differing opinions on the curriculum implementation, affecting instructional methods, school objectives, and aims for their students Alnahdi, Saloviita, & Elhadi (2019).

According to Sali and Marasigan (2020), the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines' Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) program needs proficient Madrasah instructors, or Asatidz, to be the primary program implementers. The Asatidz are supposed to be curriculum designers, planners, implementers, and assessors who are cognizant of the educational approaches and subject matter that students will be using. In the context of the Arabic language, although many "*hafiz and hafizah*" can easily recall the Quran, it is clear that the majority of pupils still struggle with it. Even more, kids who study Arabic are still unable to learn the language proficiently. This occurs because they lack the confidence and enthusiasm necessary to learn Arabic. Consequently, they are unable to fully study Arabic because of their lack of energy, and effort. The effects of this issue cause pupils to struggle academically, and eventually they are unable to show their abilities Mohd, et al. (2019).

Teachers' self-efficacy is unquestionably crucial as they should not only give information or evaluate the connection and influence without fully implementing it to the students. Self-efficacy, as defined by Bandura

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(1997), is the belief that individuals have in their ability to plan and carry out necessary actions to achieve specific goals. Multiple studies have shown a link between student success and high teacher self-confidence by Denzine, Cooney, & McKenzie, (2005); Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, (2007); Zee & Komen, (2016). Moreover, the level of confidence that Arabic teachers have in themselves is connected to the amount of work needed to accomplish a task according to Zee & Koomen (2016).

The research examines how Arabic teachers in the Philippines utilize the self-efficacy framework to support and implement instructional activities to achieve student objectives. This section intends to provide insights not only into the effective teaching strategies and learning processes but also into the importance of self-confidence in the lives of Filipino-Arabic educators. The findings will assist educational stakeholders in understanding the self-efficacy dimension of Filipino-Arabic teachers. They will also enhance their capacity to teach and improve the performance of Arabic-speaking students.

OBJECTIVES

The general objective of this study is to determine the self-efficacy framework among Arabic teachers in Davao del Norte, Philippines.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The research carried out by Flores (2018), revealed that the capacity of teachers to handle difficult students and handle those situations is an intricate process that greatly impacts their level of resilience. In the same context, Almsaiden (2024), argued that educators need to take on the responsibility of making improved decisions when handling students' situations, demonstrating their dedication to reaching objectives, and supporting learners in overcoming feelings of inadequacy or difficulty in learning. This aligns with the study of Asli et al. (2021), which emphasizes the importance of decision-making as a crucial cognitive function for humans. It is essential for processing information and carrying out sustainable actions. Decision-making is a logical procedure that results in the selection of a preferred option or multiple alternatives. Arabic teachers have been introduced to various teaching strategies to enhance critical thinking skills in dealing with their students. Educational programs integrate thinking growth with various disciplines. Making decisions is a continuous process that starts with recognizing, characterizing, and imagining the issue, and ends with selecting a course of action and accepting accountability for the outcome. High cognitive abilities are required for decision-making and problem-solving processes, regardless of their role or career in society.

Moreover, Kdough (2022) emphasized that the teachers with high levels of self-efficacy were adept at establishing a safe, trustworthy, and encouraging learning environment. The necessity to reconsider roles and duties to maintain students' comfort was brought to light by the student-centered character of research methods. The study of Adnan, Mamat, Ibrahim & Mohamed (2019) focused on Arabic educators' self-confidence perceptions regarding behavior management and classroom control. Teachers with high self-efficacy had greater faith in their capacity to manage disruptive conduct and create a positive learning atmosphere. Arabic educators feel confident in their ability to effectively manage student behavior, supported by strong evidence linking self-efficacy in behavioral management to successful problem prevention in various settings.

Alharthi and Alzahrani (2022) affirmed that teachers who encourage parents to participate in school activities aid their children's academic achievement. The results emphasize the importance of building connections with parents, based on research showing how Arabic teachers' belief in their ability to motivate parents can lead to increased support for their children's education. This research highlights the significance of parental involvement in creating a supportive learning atmosphere.

Consequently, the study of Alsubhi, Adnan, bin Yusof, Awae, and Abuhassna (2023) on the impact of teacher collaboration on teaching strategies in Arabic language schools suggests that a teacher may be able to improve the quality of their instruction by seeking out resources and collaborating with colleagues. The study emphasizes the importance of sharing teaching resources and methods, as demonstrated by Arabic teachers' willingness to participate in inter-school activities and provide useful materials. This research highlights the significance of teacher collaboration in establishing a dynamic and supportive learning atmosphere.

As posited by Chambers (2019), teachers can significantly improve student outcomes by adeptly utilizing school resources and actively engaging parents in school activities. The study underscores the necessity for teachers to take the initiative in developing lesson plans, as evidenced by the strong self-confidence exhibited by Arabic teachers in resource utilization and parental involvement. This research underscores the critical role of these elements in fostering a supportive learning environment.

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Moreover, Abu Shamon (2021), corroborated the influence of religious and community involvement in Arabic-speaking educational institutions. According to the research, Arabic teachers who actively involve religious and community entities in school initiatives witness heightened student engagement and improved academic outcomes. The findings of the study underscore the necessity of establishing strong connections with external stakeholders, emphasizing that teachers' confidence in their ability to facilitate community involvement is crucial for developing a constructive educational atmosphere.

Likewise, the study conducted by Al Ahbabi (2019) aligns with this perspective, examining how Arabic teachers collaborate with diverse stakeholders, including private enterprises and parents, to improve school programs and meet specific needs. Research indicates that teachers who actively involve stakeholders in policy and decision-making processes tend to achieve better student outcomes and foster a more positive school climate. Consistent with findings that highlight the willingness of Arabic teachers to engage stakeholders and incorporate parents into classroom regulations, the importance of collaboration with external partners is emphasized. This research highlights the critical role of external partnerships in advancing education and facilitating school restructuring initiatives.

METHODOLOGY

The study's design employed a quantitative, correlational, non-experimental research methodology. The rationale behind selecting this approach is to examine the correlation between a few parameters and ascertain their magnitude. The structured 30-item questionnaire used in this study was administered to Arabic language instructors in Davao del Norte, Philippines. The efficacy framework of the respondents selected through random sampling was identified using an Exploratory Factor Analysis. The Kaiser Meyer Olkin (KMO) test was used to determine the appropriateness of the dataset for factor analysis and the strength of the correlation among the underlying factors. A KMO value closer to 1 indicates a more suitable dataset with adequate shared variance for meaningful factor extraction. Bartlett's test of Sphericity was applied to evaluate the dataset's dimensional reduction suitability further. By plotting the eigenvalues of the factors in descending order on a Scree Plot, the optimum number of factors to retain was determined.

Data Collection Methods

1. **Permission and Ethical Considerations:** The manuscript contains all required standard declarations. Participants gave their informed consent, confidentiality was ensured, and the study met ethical standards.
2. **Distribution and Administration:** The questionnaires were distributed in either printed or electronic form (google form), depending on the availability. To guarantee correctness during completion, the directions were unambiguous.
3. **Data Retrieval:** The completed questionnaires were gathered at the conclusion and examined in light of additional research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data exploration and explanation are the main goals of this section. In order to apply the Kaiser Meals Olkin Measure Test (KMo) and Bartlett scaling, this section examines the research study's data and conclusions using the statistical software SPSS. 150 people teaching within Davao del Norte, Philippines, participated in the study.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.656
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4263.100
	df	435
	Sig.	.000

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's Test

The outcomes of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity are displayed in Table 1. A KMO score of 0.656 suggests that the sample size is adequate for identifying self-efficacy factors, showing a moderate correlation. Moreover, Bartlett's Test of Sphericity provided a value of 4263.100 with a significance level below .000, indicating that the data is appropriate for studying the self-efficacy

framework among Arabic educators. The results from Bartlett's Test of Sphericity also suggest that the self-efficacy framework is evident among Arabic teachers in Davao del Norte.

Figure 1. Scree Plot Rotated Component Matrix

Scree Plot

The total variance was depicted by the Scree Plot, showing Eigenvalues against all factors graphically. This graph shows how Eigenvalues are decreasing and aids in evaluating the importance of each component. The Scree Plot is useful in determining the number of factors to keep, with the inflection point showing where the curve levels off. In this research, the curve begins to level off at component eight when Eigenvalues below one start to emerge. If the measurements of a dimension are less than the minimum requirement, that dimension will be removed. As a result, only eight factors were included in the analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix

Item	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 4:	As an Arabic Teacher, I make decisions in a deliberate, logical process.	.883	Decision-Making and Resilience
Item 5:	As an Arabic Teacher, overcome the most difficult students.	.862	
Item 3:	As an Arabic Teacher, express views freely on important school matters.	.801	
Item 1:	As an Arabic Teacher, influence the decisions that are made in the Arabic school.	.742	
Item 2:	As an Arabic Teacher, remain calm when I have to make decisions very quickly.	.629	

Table 2: Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of Decision-making and Resilience

Decision-Making and Resilience. Table 2 provides the qualities that emphasize the rational decision-making, resilience, and influence of the Arabic Teachers in the context of an educational institution. Item No. 4 or “making decisions in a deliberate, logical process” showed the highest loading item with a score of 0.883. Item No.5 showed a factor loading of .862 implies that Arabic teachers overcome the most difficult students. Item No. 3 showed that Arabic Teachers express their views freely on important school matters with a factor loading of .801. Item No. 1 showed that Arabic Teachers influence the decisions that are made in the Arabic school with a factor loading of .742 and lastly, Item No. 2 showed that Arabic Teachers remain calm when they have to make decisions very quickly with a factor loading of .629. The findings of the study imply that capacity development focused on decision-making even under pressure could enhance resilience among Arabic teachers. The Arabic teacher makes decisions in a deliberate, logical process that overcomes the most difficult students and expresses views freely on important school matters. They also influence the decisions that are made in the Arabic school and maintain calmness when they need to quickly decide.

This finding corroborates the study of Flores (2018) and Almsaiden (2024) highlighting the importance of teachers' resilience in handling difficult students. They emphasize the need for improved decision-making, dedication to objectives, and support for learners. In addition, Asli et al. (2021) highlight the significance of decision-making as a crucial cognitive function. Arabic teachers are encouraged to enhance critical thinking skills through various teaching strategies. High cognitive abilities are essential for decision-making and problem-solving processes, regardless of their role or career in society.

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 28:	As an Arabic Teacher, make school a safe place for learning.	.939	Supportive Learning Environment
Item 30:	As an Arabic Teacher, make sure that children feel comfortable inside the school.	.916	
Item 29:	As an Arabic Teacher, let students feel trust in teachers.	.755	
Item 18:	As an Arabic Teacher, assist parents in helping their children do well in school.	.686	

Table 3. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of a Supportive Learning Environment

Supportive Learning Environment. Table 3 displays items 28, 30, 29, and 18, showcasing the Arabic teacher's dedication to establishing a supportive and secure learning environment. Item No. 28, with the strongest factor loading at 0.939, indicates that the *teacher's ability to make the school a safe space for learning is a leading component of this factor*. Item No. 30 also showed a high-loading score of 0.916 suggesting that the *teacher's role is essential for student's comfort inside the school's premises*. These results show that prioritizing safety, comfort, and trust-building strategies in school policies creates a caring and encouraging learning atmosphere for their students.

It endorsed the research carried out by Kdouh, (2022) that explores, specifically in Arabic language classrooms, the link between teacher self-confidence and the creation of a conducive learning atmosphere. Teachers with high levels of self-efficacy were adept at establishing a safe, trustworthy, and encouraging learning environment. As a result, the results showed how dedicated their Arabic teachers are to working to provide a proper learning environment. The necessity to reconsider roles and duties to maintain students' comfort was brought to light by the student-centered character of research methods.

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 9:	control disruptive behavior in the classroom.	.819	Behavioral Management
Item 10:	prevent problem behavior on the school grounds.	.749	
Item 27:	make school a safe place for learning.	.685	

Table 4. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of a Behavioral Management

Behavioral Management. In items 9, 10, and 27, over *two-thirds of Arabic teachers thought they could handle student behavior well* presented in Table 4. Item No. 9 with the highest factor loading that the *effectiveness of the teacher in handling disorderly manners is significant to managing behaviors in the classroom*. The results suggest that the ability of Arabic educators to implement structured management behavior is vital to shaping the student's conduct.

This is supported by the study of Adnan, Mamat, Ibrahim & Mohamed (2019) focused on Arabic educators' self-confidence perceptions regarding behavior management and classroom control. Teachers with high self-efficacy had greater faith in their capacity to manage disruptive conduct and create a positive learning atmosphere. Arabic educators feel confident in their ability to effectively manage student behavior, supported by strong evidence linking self-efficacy in behavioral management to successful problem prevention in various settings.

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 19:	make parents interested in coming to school.	.814	Parental Involvement
Item 20:	encourage parents to make follow-ups about their children's progress.	.627	
Item 6:	promote Arabic learning even when there is a lack of support from home.	.555	

Item 7:	motivate students who show low interest in learning the Arabic language.	.539	
Item 21:	welcome parents in school.	.517	

Table 5. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of a Parental Involvement

Parental Involvement. Table 5 shows that *Arab educators are highly confident in their ability to engage parents or encourage them to participate in the process* when it comes to items 19, 20, 6, 7, and 21. Based on the findings, item no. 19 with the highest factor loading of 0.814, indicated that *parental involvement is primarily driven by the Arabic teacher, which is essential for improving student engagement and academic performance.*

The same is true in the study conducted by Alharthi and Alzahrani (2022) on the investigation of Arabic educators' opinions regarding parental involvement and its impact on students' development, teachers who encourage parents to participate in school activities and invite them to ensure their children's academic achievement, according to studies. The results emphasize the importance of building connections with parents, based on research showing how Arabic teachers' belief in their ability to motivate parents can lead to increased support for their children's education. This research highlights the significance of parental involvement in creating a supportive learning atmosphere.

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 5:	do not rely on the instructional materials that the school offers.	.760	Resourcefulness and Collaboration
Item 25:	mingle with other schools in some school activities.	.741	
Item 14:	introduce instructional materials that I believe useful to my colleagues.	.568	

Table 6. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of Resourcefulness and Collaboration

Resourcefulness and Collaboration. According to Table 6, the confidence level of Arabic educators in using a variety of sources and working with colleagues is shown by items 15, 25, and 14. Though the loadings of this factor are not as high with factors 1 to 4, the results suggest that items 5 and 25 have high-loading factors (0.760 and 0.741). This suggests that the *Arabic instructors have a strong ability to use resources and collaborate well with others, which are critical to improving the school environment.*

This supports a study on the impact of teacher collaboration on teaching strategies in Arabic language schools by Alsubhi, Adnan, bin Yusof, Awae, and Abuhassna (2023). The study suggests that a teacher may be able to improve the quality of their instruction by seeking out resources and collaborating with colleagues. The study emphasizes the importance of sharing teaching resources and methods, as demonstrated by Arabic teachers' willingness to participate in inter-school activities and provide useful materials. This research highlights the significance of teacher collaboration in establishing a dynamic and supportive learning atmosphere.

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 17:	involve parents in school activities.	.863	School Resources and Instruction
Item 16:	make use of the school equipment in teaching.	.594	
Item 12:	make initiatives in making instructional Arabic materials.	.534	

Table 7. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of a School Resources and Instruction

School Resources and Instruction. Table 7 illustrates that item 17 "*Involve parents in school activities*" shows the highest factor loading of 0.863, Item 16 "*Make use of the school equipment in teaching*" got a higher factor loading of .594, and Item 12 "*Make initiatives in making instructional Arabic materials*" with .534.

This indicates that Arabic teachers when it comes to school resources and instruction involve parents in school activities, they make use of the school equipment in teaching and initiate making instructional Arabic materials. This is a considerable degree of self-assurance among Arabic teachers regarding their ability to effectively utilize resources and involve parents in the educational process. Item No. 17 with the highest factor loading contributes greatly to this factor. This indicates that *Arabic educators can leverage school resources and instructional strategies to collaborate closely with parents, enhancing students' educational experiences.*

This finding corroborates the research conducted by Chambers (2019), which examined the correlation between student achievement in Arabic schools, parental involvement, and the use of school resources and teaching methodologies. The researchers concluded that teachers can significantly improve student outcomes by adeptly utilizing school resources and actively engaging parents in school activities. The study underscores the necessity for teachers to take the initiative in developing lesson plans, as evidenced by the strong self-confidence exhibited by Arabic teachers in resource utilization and parental involvement. This research underscores the critical role of these elements in fostering a supportive learning environment.

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 22:	Involve community groups in school activities.	.843	Community Engagement
Item 23:	Involve religious groups in working with the school.	.747	

Table 8. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of a Community Engagement

Community Engagement. Table 8 illustrates that items 22 “*Involve community groups in school activities*” with the highest factor loading at 0.843 and 23 “*Involve religious groups in working with the school*” with a high factor loading of 0.747, indicating that Arabic educators possess a robust conviction in their ability to stimulate community participation, which is essential for enhancing the educational experience and cultivating a supportive learning environment. This implies that Arabic teachers stimulate community participation in which they involve community groups in school activities and religious groups in working with the school.

This supports the study conducted by Abu Shamon (2021), which examines the influence of religious and community involvement in Arabic-speaking educational institutions. According to the research, Arabic teachers who actively involve religious and community entities in school initiatives witness heightened student engagement and improved academic outcomes. The results underscore the necessity of establishing strong connections with external stakeholders, emphasizing that teachers' confidence in their ability to facilitate community involvement is crucial for developing a constructive educational atmosphere.

Table 9. Rotated component matrix with grouped attributes of External Partnerships

Items	Attributes	Loading	Factor
Item 26:	Invite stakeholders to help our school needs.	.710	External Partnerships
Item 11:	Involve parents in constructing the classroom discipline policies and procedures.	.675	
Item 24:	Involve private companies and other businesses in school activities.	.626	

External Partnerships. Table 9 illustrates that item 26 “*Invite stakeholders to help our school needs*” got the highest factor loading with .710. Item 11 “*Involve parents in constructing the classroom discipline policies and procedures*” got .675, and Item 24 “*Involve private companies and other businesses in school activities*” with .626 factor loading.

This implies that Arabic teachers should have external partnerships in which they Invite stakeholders to help our school needs, and involve parents in constructing the classroom discipline policies and procedures, as well as private companies and other businesses in school activities. This indicates a robust sense of self-efficacy among Arabic teachers regarding the promotion of partnerships with various stakeholders. These findings reveal that Arabic educators possess a high degree of confidence in establishing external relationships as shown in the high factor loading of item no. 26, which is crucial for enhancing school resources and cultivating a supportive learning environment.

This finding aligns with the study conducted by Al Ahababi (2019), which examined how Arabic teachers collaborate with diverse stakeholders, including private enterprises and parents, to improve school programs and meet specific needs. Research indicates that teachers who actively involve stakeholders in policy and decision-making processes tend to achieve better student outcomes and foster a more positive school climate. Consistent with findings that highlight the willingness of Arabic teachers to engage stakeholders and incorporate parents into classroom regulations, the importance of collaboration with external partners is emphasized. This research highlights the critical role of external partnerships in advancing education and facilitating school restructuring initiatives.

STUDY FRAMEWORK

Presented in Figure 2 is the framework developed based on the findings. The researchers found that the factors for the Self-efficacy framework among Arabic Teachers are (1) Decision-Making and Resilience, (2) Supportive Learning Environment, (3) Behavioral Management, (4) Parental Involvement, (5) Resourcefulness and Collaboration (6) School Resources and Instruction (7) Community Engagement and (8) External Partnerships.

Figure 2. Self-Efficacy Framework among Arabic Teachers

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, the researchers concluded that the dimensions of self-efficacy among Arabic teachers in Davao del Norte are predominantly categorized by factors such as decision-making and resilience, supportive learning environment, behavioral management, parental involvement, resourcefulness and collaboration, school resources and instruction, community engagement, and external partnerships. Also, it can be inferred from the results that the background of self-efficacy of Arabic teachers is multidimensional. Therefore, it provided information on which aspect necessitates targeted interventions and support mechanisms that will enhance the efficacy of the Arabic Teachers as a professional and as an individual.

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